

PEDAGOGY OF COOPERATION IN TEACHING RUSSIAN TO STUDENTS IN GROUPS WITH A NON-RUSSIAN LANGUAGE OF INSTRUCTION

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Annotation: This article is a synthesis of the theoretical and practical findings of a large-scale scientific investigation of the topic of joint education in comprehensive Russian schools of international students who do not speak Russian as a native language and Russian native speakers. The study identifies the key steps in overcoming migrant children's assimilation challenges in Russian schools. The effectiveness of methodologists' and teachers' attempts to address coeducational deficiencies is examined in this research. Traditionally, these issues have been addressed using a distinguishing process. Our research, on the other hand, presents an integrative approach to solving the aforementioned issues. A dominant novel element of the work is an integrative approach. The study's authors identified a set of teaching principles for the Russian language. In this article about pedagogy of cooperation in teaching Russian to students in groups with a non-Russian language of instruction.

Keywords: *Non-native, concept, learning, multinational class, Russian, teaching students, pedagogy, cooperation, non-russian.*

Introduction. According to recent data, the modern world community lives in a dynamic migration flow, resulting in a multi-ethnic, multi-religious, and multi-lingual world social space. As a result, tactics for the growth of the social, economic, political, and spiritual sectors of human life have changed.

These new paradigms are critical for the development and upbringing of future personalities capable of successfully living, working, and communicating in an international society. In the last decade, Russia has experienced a large influx of migrants from neighboring countries, as well as an increase in the percentage of internal migration. As a result of these tendencies, not only did the country's large megacities - the region's capitals - develop a multinational and polyconfessional society, but also the multinational and polyconfessional atmosphere in Russian schools. In certain situations, up to 40% of the student body is made up of children who do not speak Russian well. Inophones, or migrant children, are the term for these students.

Migratory children traditionally strive to lead a habitual way of life in a new place, based on their past experiences while also adjusting to their migrant reality. They draw from their native people's spiritual experiences and behavioral customs. Migrant children are deprived of their usual social surroundings and

social roles from the moment they seek to adapt to their new position. This approach to living in Russia results in a "culture shock" when confronted with Russian reality, when immigrant children's accustomed life standards and values lose their meaning. Furthermore, a family's different religion can be a barrier to adjusting to a new environment, such as a school environment, while learning a new language of communication. Religious inconsistencies influence a child's worldview development, resulting in behavior that is consistent with specific dogmas and beliefs. And the need to keep one's religion alive further worsens the plight of such children in a different ethno-cultural setting, particularly at school. The general low rate of advancement of migrant children, caused, to an equal degree, by poor knowledge of the language of communication and deficiencies in the development of their intellectual region, was a regular feature of the existing situation (thinking, logic, imagination).

The impending educational crisis has aided the establishment of a new educational paradigm based on the premise that ongoing ethnic processes must be considered in the formation and upbringing of a person capable of living and working in a multinational and multi-confessional society. Simultaneously, one of the most important responsibilities of modern approaches is to teach Russian as a key subject for understanding other disciplines. The practice of conducting additional RFL classes for migrant children began in 2000, when the Moscow Committee of Education issued an order providing for the opening of groups for the study of Russian as a foreign language (RFL) with a teaching load of two hours per week, which gave rise to the practice of conducting additional RFL classes for migrant children. The remainder of the country followed the capital district's lead. Additional classes with migrant children are not enough to attain their level of language competency, allowing them to learn the topic on an equal footing with native speakers, as practice has proved throughout time.

Teaching the Russian language in polyconfessional classes using integrative technologies 49 such students from the broader educational process in traditional lessons in common with native speakers. The development and introduction of new teaching aids for foreign students, such as educational programs and educational-methodological complexes for Russian as RFL, as well as teaching aids for additional education for migrant children and teacher guidelines, has also been a priority area of research. These technologies are presently employed in most Russian schools during supplementary RFL sessions with migrant students, as well as a modified approach to traditional lessons with native speakers. It's

worth noting that traditional classes in international classes use the Federal Educational Standards-recommended training methods.

Conclusion. According to academics, a combination of the following activities can be used to organize the teaching of the Russian language to migrant children: 1) linguoculturology projects, 2) class/school communicative games, 3) polite behavior contests that appeal to migrant children's native culture, 4) a school linguo-regional journal that demonstrates the mutual influence of numerous national cultures and the Russian language, and so on. This strategy allows for the employment of a unique manner of creating educational events that is particularly significant in a multi-religious school setting and adds to the establishment of an open communication scenario. Despite several experimental studies on the subject, a number of issues related to the development of the content of the subject "Russian Language" in international classes have remained unsolved to this point. The crux of the problem is the structure of Russian language classes taught in conjunction with native speakers.

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